

LATEST: An Erasmus+ Project On Local-focused AgTech Education For Successful Agricultural Transitions

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Introduction

Agriculture is the most exposed economic sector to climate change patterns with cascade effects on agro-ecosystems functioning and food security. At the same time, agriculture is considered one of the major contributors to climate change. Innovations are thus needed to adapt agricultural systems to extreme climate events, but also to mitigate climate change by reducing greenhouse gas (GHGs) emissions, as well as to increase carbon stocks. All these goals are expected to contribute to the resilience and sustainability of food production within the Farm to Fork EU strategy. The whole process of shifting from current mainstream agricultural practices to more sustainable ones is known as agricultural transition, encompassing agro-ecological, climate-smart and/or energetic transitions. Several research papers and reports have underlined the role of agricultural technologies (hereafter AgTech) as one of the main levers, together with the institutional innovations, to reach successful agricultural transitions. AgTech includes both hardware and software innovations, such as traditional and automated equipment, farm management information systems, and other technologies overcoming the principles of precision agriculture to monitor and manage farming practices in their environmental and socio-technical context. In this vein, AgTech used at the farm level and beyond are expected to improve the use and management of natural resources while increasing productivity and reducing trade-offs, such as GHG emissions. However, innovations and technologies require mastery and the learning of new skills by farmers and other operators of the agricultural sector. To face this need, multiple training and educational programs have emerged. Although, programs and skills remain scattered across countries and specific technologies. The LATEST Project aims at provide an exhaustive overview of educational and training programs in AgTech as a basis to design multidisciplinary innovative, locally fine-tuned academic programs to develop, implement and adapt AgTech for European agricultural stakeholders – including manufacturers, farmers, public and private technical services – in the transition towards sustainable and climate-smart agricultural systems. The main beneficiaries will be students, life-long learners, partners of the project, associated partners, and, according to the strategy of open-access results, the whole agricultural community. The overall expected result is to contribute positively to the diffusion of AgTech as a supporting tool for the mitigation of climate change in the regions targeted by the project.

Materials and Methods

The project is organized into five Work Packages (WP) and 10 associated project results (Figure 13). WP1 aims to provide a benchmark of existing and emerging training programs. Data from the benchmark will be mapped to highlight a possible relationship with different soil and climate contexts and/or agricultural systems. WP2 focuses on the demand of the labour market and stakeholders (industries, institutions, NGOs, farmers, students, etc.). The data collected will draw the contours of future workers' required qualifications to work appropriately with AgTech in the next 15 years. The comparison between the results of WP1 and WP2 will provide the background to develop new curricula, based on up-to-date content and innovative teaching method and vision. WP3 deals with curricula development. It will

validate the hypotheses made in WP1 and WP2 by testing innovative contents and pedagogical tools implemented in a pilot curriculum with students of the partner Institutions. WP4 aims at ensuring strict learner-centred teaching containing micro-credentials, with innovative pedagogic approaches and learning environment. Finally, WP5 supervises communication, dissemination and exploitation of the result of the project. The LATEST project involves as partners the Polytechnic Institute UniLaSalle in Beauvais, France (coordinator), the University of Udine in Italy, the University of Hohenheim in Germany, the BOKU University in Austria and the Harper Adams University in UK. Moreover, 14 associated partners (manufacturers as individuals or in an associated form, farmers associations, agricultural cooperatives networks or associations of agricultural engineers) joined the project and will be particularly involved in WP1 and WP2. Eight of them are available to provide lectures and training facilities during the program and to offer internships/apprenticeships during the program.

Figure 13. Workflow and list of the workpackages (WP) and related project results (PR) of the LATEST project.

Results and Conclusions

After the appointment of Erasmus+ Programme, the project started on November 2021. According to the target dates reported in the GANTT diagram, intermediate achievements deal with the design of the conceptual database schemes and related monitoring strategies for existing teaching programs, infrastructural equipment, digital platforms and software, active learning experience, and requirements of the labour market.

Designed during the COVID-19 pandemic emergency, the LATEST project crosses the topics of the PNRR Agritech National Centre, offering challenging opportunities to exploit these strategic goals in an educational perspective. Beyond its specific objective, it can also represent a platform of discussion on AgTech both within the community of agronomists and between agronomists and agricultural engineers with the aim to share knowledge and approaches towards agricultural transitions.

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